

Baltic German and Baltic German Literature. Language History and Autobiographical Writing from Transnational and Regional Perspective

Version 1

Description

This DMP is developed in the framework of the project "Baltic German and Baltic German Literature" (Izp-2025/1-0170). The aim of the project is to complete the history of the Baltic Germans both in the Baltic and German cultural context. While the linguistic part connects conceptual novelty with a modern approach to the language history, highlighting regionality, contact linguistics, as well as aspects of applied linguistics, the literary research (primarily: female autobiography) contributes to the international discourse of literary studies.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science | | LCS

Grant

Baltic German and Baltic German Literature. Language History and Autobiographical Writing from Transnational and Regional Perspective (Izp-2025/1-0170)

Researchers

Ineta Balode (0000-0001-9552-5173), Dzintra Lele-Rozentāle (0000-0003-3181-6929), Tatjana Kuharenoka

Organizations

Univeristy of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Baltic German and Baltic German Literature. Language History and Autobiographical Writing from Transnational and Regional Perspective](#)

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Organizations:

[Univeristy of Latvia](#)

Contact: [Balode Ineta \(ineta.balode@lu.lv\)](#)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: [Latvian Council of Science | | LCS](#)

Grants: [Baltic German and Baltic German Literature. Language History and Autobiographical Writing from Transnational and Regional Perspective \(Izp-2025/1-0170\)](#)

Project:

3. License

License: [CC-BY-4.0](#)

Access Rights: [Public](#)

Publication Date: [2025-11-11](#)

4. Templates

Descriptions

Interactive study material (H5P)

The interactive material (H5P) supports the students studying the German language history and literature, especially in the Baltic region.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

This interactive material includes bibliographical data about German language history and literature in the Baltic region.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Textual data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- PDF
- Others

H5P

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

100

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

students of humanities, general public

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

DataverseLV

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2029-01-01

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Ineta Balode (0000-0001-9552-5173)

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

Collection of Theses

This collection contains abstracts of presentations given at the annual international academic conference held by University of Latvia and documents ongoing research into German language and literature in the Baltic region.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

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Documentation of research results

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CERIF (Common European Research Information Format)

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